

THE FUNCTIONAL EVIDENCE DISCUSSION FORUM LAUNCH 2024

POLL OUTCOMES SUMMARY REPORT

Thank you to all that participated in the Functional Evidence Discussion Forum Launch!

Summary

Despite its many benefits, functional evidence is one of the least used evidence categories for variant classification, and represents an untapped resource for resolving uncertainty in diagnostic genomics. A Needs Survey performed by the MAVE Education Project identified that training in functional evidence use was needed, and during a resulting workshop we asked if there was support for a continuing discussion forum to support peer based learning. 91% of participants supported a functional evidence discussion forum, prompting the initiation of the functional evidence discussion forum.

Figure 1. Results from Workshop June 2024 polling interest in a Functional Evidence discussion Forum

The MAVE Education project launched the functional evidence discussion forum on the 16th October, online via zoom. The launch incorporated substantial consultation/polling of the participants to inform the future forum format and delivery. This report summarises the launch consultation outcomes, specifically the participant opinion captured via the polls and discussion in the meeting.

The participants

76 people registered for the functional evidence forum, with 78 participants signing in on the day.

Figure 2. Primary professional position as indicated by the participants

56/76 registrants indicated they currently perform clinical variant classification (determine variant pathogenicity in a diagnostic setting and 60/76 indicated they evaluate functional evidence for the purpose of clinical variant classification.

Figure 5. Participants

indicated how often they would prefer to attend the Functional Evidence Discussion Forum meetings.

We asked if they (the participants) would be interested to use any of the following mechanisms to discuss functional evidence (ie alternative FE forum platforms)

Table 1. Interest in additional mechanisms for forum discussion.

Method	# voted*
A communication channel	29
A web-based forum (message board)	32 (54%)
Microsoft teams-based	27
TOTAL	59

*voters could select more than one option, so totals votes could equal great than the total voters

Noting that in the chat a few people expressly requested NO use of Teams in the chat. There is reasonable support for an online platform, potentially a low effort forum is the simplest and could trial to see actual uptake?

Terms

We asked a poll question regarding sharing patient information, but this was complicated as the participants could only select one option (really should have been able to select multiple). Only 17 selected an option, but of those 5 felt it necessary to say that they will not share patient identifying information, 8 said that they can discuss specific variants with the patient information removed. We asked in the chat for supplemental opinion also, and specifically asked if people agreed that we could **share variant and phenotype information, and 14 agreed.**

We also asked if we should ‘approve/confirm/vote’ on rules or guidelines for what we can and can’t do in the forum, 6 people agreed in the chat, and 7 in the poll, along with 6 indicating that they are unsure. Only 2 people on poll said that No, they wouldn’t. **General consensus support drafting guidelines for the forum.** The basis being that we can share variant/phenotype information, NO patient information is to be shared.

Scope

Figure 6. Indicated interest in nominated types of presentations.

Topics

Figure 7. Indicated interest in nominated presentation topics.

Additional suggested topics were

- Practical cases for using functional assays for variants using MAVE database
- MAVE assays vs proteomics - pros and cons, concordance
- Application of PM1 for critical protein regions (based on functional evidence)

Presenting

Many people are comfortable to nominate variants, but only a portion are comfortable to present. Generally speaking they would like support/a template to present. 13 said that they would present though, and another 9 may nominate an assay for discussion (Table 2), so **there is sufficient support that we can ask curators to present**, and to guide what we discuss (and hopefully share the load for presenting).

Table 2. Are participants likely to be willing to present an assay for review, and under which conditions?

	# voting
I would be comfortable to nominate an assay for someone else to present	9
I would be comfortable to present an assay/variant if there were a template	5
I would be comfortable to present an assay/variant with support from a facilitator	8
I would like to present an assay for discussion on my terms	1
No	13

Recording

We asked if you (participants) comfortable **with this forum session** being recorded? and if so, how should the recording be used? And, generally, are you comfortable with the forum being recorded? and if so, how should the recordings be used? Participants were generally comfortable with the forum being recorded. 7 participants did not want sharing, in this case will need to consider if majority wins, and if so, how we can address the concerns of those that do not want the recording to be shared.

Figure 8. Poll regarding consent to record the Functional Evidence Discussion Forum Launch Session, asking regarding sharing the Launch recording.

Figure 9. Poll regarding the continuing approach to recording the Functional Evidence Discussion Forum, including querying the sharing of the forum recordings.

Overall outcomes

Based on the poll results and considering the consultation to date, we propose the following recommendations for the functional evidence discussion forum.

1. Curators are highly represented in the participant group (most interest/relevance for this group), however a range of other expertise was present/interested including pathology and research professionals. Should likely target to curators.
2. Confidence for functional evidence evaluation was middle of the range, most participants indicated 3/5 (5 being the highest comfort level).
3. Most participants supported a quarterly online seminar

4. An online forum (potentially a discussion page) could be useful, and initiating a low impact option may be worth trialling. The continuation on this might be dependent on the engagement.
5. We should draft a 'rules' for the Functional Evidence Discussion Forum
6. Generally speaking it was agreed that NO patient information could be shared, but variant and phenotype information sharing would be fine. Discussing public/published data would be no problem. These conditions are perfectly suitable for the Functional Evidence Discussion Forum.
7. Suggest building a template for presenting an assay for discussion is a good idea
8. A wide range of topics and presentation types are useful
9. We should recruit from the participants to nominate assays and to present them for discussion, this will identify most useful discussions but also support sharing knowledge
10. General support was indicated for recording and sharing, suggest establishing consent for recording sharing from the presenter on a case-by-case basis is appropriate.

Proposed future directions

- Will draft a proposal for the Functional Evidence Discussion Forum ongoing delivery
- Will report to the working group for discussion on the proposal, sharing these results to support their consideration
- Will build rules, and presentation template, and potentially initiate an online discussion page
- We will build on the evaluation approach, depending on the working group recommendations
- Will share the slides from the workshop with the participants

Additional analysis?

- Text mine to extract a 'representative' objective from the participant suggestions

Conclusion

Participant polls collected during the launch of the Functional Evidence Discussion Forum were very informative and inform participant preferences for the ongoing Forum. Based on the poll results, we will draft a proposal detailing the Forum format for 2025, which will be presented for discussion with the MAVE Education Project Working Group. We will then deliver the next session of the Functional Evidence Discussion Forum early in 2025 following participant preferences. The program will be evaluated according to the program evaluation plan, including assessing participant confidence again at the end of 2025.

Thank you to all of the participants in the Functional Evidence Forum

We would like to thank you, the participants and members of the diagnostic genomics community, for your support and engagement. Your consultation is very helpful in guiding the direction of the MAVE Education project. If you have any questions on the activities of the MAVE Education project team, please contact Rehan Villani, Project co-ordinator, rehan.villani@qimrberghofer.edu.au.